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Horizon Europe project AGEMERA: Combining novel methodologies for agile exploration and geomodelling of critical raw materials deposits

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Introduction

The name of the AGEMERA project stems from the words "Agile Exploration and Geo-modelling for European Critical Raw Materials" (grant agreement N° 101058178). AGEMERA (Holma et al., 2022; Peytcheva et al., 2022) has 20 partners from 10 European countries (Finland, Estonia, Poland, Germany, Netherlands, Hungary, Bulgaria, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Spain) and 1 external country (Zambia). The project's goal is to improve the regional and local mineral system models for ore deposits associated with critical raw materials (CRMs) in (1) the Peräpohja-Kuusamo schist belts in Finland (*orogenic Au deposits with atypical Co-enriched metal association*), (2) the Fore-Sudetic Monocline district in Poland (*Kupferschiefer-type stratabound Cu and Ag deposits with Co, Zn, Ni, Mo and V enrichments*), (3) the Jajce and Posušje districts in Bosnia-Herzegovina (*karst bauxite deposits*), (4) the Apuseni-Banat-Timok-Srednogorie belt in Bulgaria (*locally PGE-enriched porphyry Cu, epithermal Au, and Fe-oxide Cu-Au deposits*), (5) the Iberian Pyrite Belt in Spain (*Ni-Cu-Co mineralisation*), (6) the Erzgebirge district in Germany (*Li and Sn mineralisations, associated with, e.g., post-magmatic greisens*), and (7) four districts in Zambia (*sediment-hosted stratiform Cu-Co in the Copperbelt and North-Western domes regions and Ni, Mn, Li and REE in the Central and Luapula provinces*). The Assarel open-pit porphyry Cu and Lubin underground Kupferschiefer-type Cu mines are among the most notable deposits studied in the project.

Study methods and goals

Several geological, geochemical, and geophysical field methods will be applied to provide input for laboratory-based studies and computer-based modelling of the selected mineral systems. The studied topics include dating the mineralisation processes and establishing improved models for fluid and magma pathways, such as transcrustal-scale terrane boundaries, thrust zones, oroclinal bends, basin-controlling master faults, and local structural controls (for example, see Palinkaš et al., 2022). Additional data will be sourced from the literature and databases. The ultimate objective is to identify new areas for CRM exploration, especially in previously overlooked regions. In geophysics, the project focuses on developing further three novel non-destructive survey methods: 1) passive seismic methods, 2) multi-sensing drone system combining magnetic, radiometric, and electromagnetic sensing and 3) multidetector cosmic-ray muon imaging (muography) for density mapping in various dimensions. The other goal is to use acquired geophysical data to improve the understanding of mineralisation footprints and develop regional and local exploration tools.

The collaboration also focuses on data fusion, small-group interviews, public awareness events, social-licence-to-operate studies, launching university courses, results dissemination, and science outreach. As a whole, the project's goals are: (i) Identify new areas and re-evaluate old mining sites for their CRM potential; (ii) develop new innovative, environmentally, and socially-friendly methods for mineral exploration; (iii) survey the local communities' concerns and hopes related to mineral exploration and mining; (iv) improve the knowledge of the importance of critical raw materials in our day-to-day lives; (v) evaluate the perception of SLO and SLE within the target regions; and (vi) Promote the utilisation of UNFC and UNRMS for the future experts.

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The 1st GeoDays of Finland is held at the Kumpula campus of the University of Helsinki, 14th–17th March 2023. The event gathers over 100 experts from different fields of geosciences to present and learn from the latest research and innovations. This publication contains the program and submitted abstracts for all the oral and poster presentations held at the event. The organizing committee would like to express gratitude to all the authors for their contributions.

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